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TREŚĆ I CHARAKTERYSTYKA PRAW DYDAKTYCZNYCH FORMOWANIE GOTOWOŚCI PRZYSZŁYCH PIELEŃNIAREK- KAWALERÓW DO DZIAŁALNOŚCI ZAWODOWEJ

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Adnotacja. W artykule uzasadniono potrzebę wprowadzenia innowacji psychologiczno-pedagogicznych w procesie kształtowania gotowości przyszłych pielęgniarek-kawalerów do aktywności zawodowej. Ustalono, że podejście prakseologiczne ma znaczny potencjał. W kontekście pedagogicznych zasad podejścia prakseologicznego wyodrębniono prawa dydaktyczne, które zostaną uwzględnione w kształceniu zawodowym przyszłych licencjatów pielęgniarstwa. Koncentruje się na charakterystyce metodologicznych i praktycznych aspektów dydaktycznych takich ustaw jak: jedność i wzajemne powiązania teorii z praktyką; jedność uczenia się i rozwoju; związek między socjalizacją i profesjonalizacją jednostki w procesie uczenia się; połączenie integracji i różnicowania; ściśle współdziałanie szkolenia teoretycznego i praktycznego. Rozważane są perspektywy, a także analizowane są praktyczne sposoby ich wprowadzenia w proces kształcenia wyższych uczelni medycznych.

Słowa kluczowe: szkolenia zawodowe, podejście prakseologiczne, prawa dydaktyczne, przyszli pielęgniarki-kawalery, gotowość do aktywności zawodowej.

THE CONTENT AND CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DIDACTIC LAWS FOR FORMING THE READINESS OF FUTURE NURSES-BACHELORS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. The article substantiates the necessity of introducing psychological and pedagogical innovations into the process of forming the readiness of future nurses-bachelors for professional activity. It has been established that the praxeological approach has significant potential. In the context of the pedagogical foundations of the praxeological approach, didactic laws were singled out that will be used in the professional training of future bachelors of nursing. It focuses on the characterization of the methodological and practical aspects of such didactic laws as: the unity and relationship of theory with practice; unity of learning and development; the relationship of socialization and professionalization of the individual in the learning process;

combination of integration and differentiation; close interaction of theoretical and practical training. Prospects are considered, and practical ways of their implementation in the educational process of higher medical educational institutions are analyzed.

Key words: professional training, praxeological approach, didactic laws, future nurses-bachelors, readiness for professional activity.

ЗМІСТ І ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ДИДАКТИЧНИХ ЗАКОНІВ ФОРМУВАННЯ ГОТОВНОСТІ МАЙБУТНІХ МЕДИЧНИХ СЕСТЕР-БАКАЛАВРІВ ДО ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ

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Анотація. У статті обґрунтовано необхідність впровадження психолого-педагогічних інновацій у процес формування готовності майбутніх медичних сестер-бакалаврів до професійної діяльності. Встановлено, що вагомим потенціалом володіє праксеологічний підхід. У контексті педагогічних засад праксеологічного підходу було виокремлено дидактичні закони, які будуть покладені у професійну підготовку майбутніх бакалаврів сестринської справи. Зосереджено увагу на характеристиці методичних і практичних аспектів таких дидактичних законів, як: єдності і взаємозв'язку теорії з практикою; єдності навчання і розвитку; взаємозв'язку соціалізації та професіоналізації особистості в процесі навчання; поєднання інтеграції та диференціації; тісної взаємодії теоретичної та практичної підготовки. Розглянуто перспективи, а також проаналізовано практичні шляхи їх впровадження в освітній процес вищих медичних навчальних закладів.

Ключові слова: професійна підготовка, праксеологічний підхід, дидактичні закони, майбутні медичні сестри-бакалаври, готовність до професійної діяльності.

Introduction. A nurse is not only the most popular among medical workers, but also acts as a kind of link between people who need medical care and a doctor as a specialist, on whom the quality of medical care for the population largely depends. Now, in connection with the COVID-19 epidemic, the requirements for the quality of professional training of nursing specialists are significantly increasing. As a result, there is a need to increase attention to the problem of organizing the educational process of students of higher educational institutions based on the application of the praxeological approach. Its implementation will lead to an increase in the quality of theoretical knowledge and improvement of practical training, which will allow future specialists to perform nursing duties at the level of professional skill.

We share the position of Y. Bogoyavlens'ka (*Bogoyavlens'ka Y. U. 2005*) that the praxeological approach is used to organize educational activities, and its use allows us to study in practice the methods of implementing effective action, to develop recommendations for optimizing the practical training of students. As N. Sackov shows, knowledge and activity are the basis of the praxeological approach “which determine the strategy of oriented praxeological actions and show how general human knowledge has

turned into a direct productive force (*Sackov N. Ya. 1998, p. 203*). We believe that the use of the theoretical foundations of the praxeological approach, first of all, requires clarification of the nature of rational activity, as well as the generalization of didactic laws, which are most consistent with praxeology.

Analysis of recent studies shows that in the works of scientists over the past 5 years (N. Dub, P. Kuzminsky, P. Sidorenko, T. Tymoshchuk, T. Chernyshenko) theoretical and practical issues of public administration of the system of development and reform of nursing education in Ukraine are highlighted. It has been established that scientific research of specialists is mainly aimed at: analysis of the potential of computer assessment of knowledge of medical college students (L. Artemchuk); formation of professional values among future nursing specialists (K. Kurenkova); development of cognitive activity (T. Teremivska); study of ideas of a healthy lifestyle in future professional activity (V. Babalich). However, a holistic and balanced approach to the substantiation and characteristics of didactic laws, which must be put as the basis for the formation of the readiness of future nurses-bachelors for professional activity in the context of a praxeological approach, has not yet been implemented.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the didactic laws, which should be used as the basis for the formation of future nurses-bachelors' readiness for professional activity.

Research methods. In order to achieve this goal, a set of methods was used, namely: theoretical - system-structural analysis and systematization of philosophical, psychological and pedagogical works, made it possible to substantiate the conceptual foundations of organizing the educational process on the basis of a praxeological approach; comparative pedagogical analysis, synthesis, deduction, induction, classification (to clarify the essence of didactic laws) pedagogical generalization, prediction and forecasting, contributed to the development of practical ways of introducing didactic laws.

Presentation of the main material. The scientific definition of “law” in a didactic textbook by I. Malafiik (Malafiik I. V. 2005) is interpreted as “practical significance, which is determined by its prognostic functions. That is, since the law reflects stability, the repeatability of connections between phenomena, it can serve as the basis for the implementation of one of the most important functions of scientific theory - scientific foresight of the course of a phenomenon, its result ” (Malafiik I. V. 2005. p. 81). The same position is declared in another textbook on pedagogy: a law is such a component of the logical structure of pedagogical science, which reflects objective, internal, essential and relatively stable connections of pedagogical phenomena, contributes to the scientific management of educational and educational activities, predicting the results of managerial decisions aimed at optimization of the content, forms and methods of this activity (Podlasyj I. P. 2001).

Fundamental for the study of the essence of didactic laws, which it is advisable to put as the basis for the formation of the readiness of future bachelors of nursing in professional activities, was V. Vykhreshch's conclusion that the law is “an internal essential connection between learning phenomena, which leads to their manifestation and development. Didactic laws are static in nature, that is, they appear as tendencies, they are characterized by variability, relative accuracy, probabilistic nature and the ability to operate accurately ” (Vykhreshch V. O. 1997, p. 48).

In practical terms, it is advisable to determine a specific list of didactic laws reflecting objective causal relationships between various elements of pedagogical

activity in the context of organizing an educational environment for future nurses-bachelors. We proceeded from the position that all laws should be consonant with the requirements of the praxeological approach. Allocating didactic laws should perform not only certain functions (explanatory, prognostic), but also describe objectively acting connections of the educational process and reflect objective relationships with the praxeological approach.

We believe that didactic laws should form a dynamic system of relations between three main factors of professional training of future specialists:

- 1) educational environment;
- 2) the content of education;
- 3) educational activities of students.

At the same time, the factors are highlighted and are considered by us as a didactic basis in the process of forming the readiness of future nursing specialists with the status of "bachelor" for professional activity. We believe that the practical significance of laws is determined by their prognostic direction, encompasses stability, repeatability of connections between phenomena. In our vision, it is the laws that act as the main ideas for the implementation of scientific foresight of the formation of future nurses-bachelors of readiness for professional activity.

We consider the professional training of future nurses-bachelors as a multifactorial phenomenon aimed at: the formation of the necessary level of knowledge, skills and abilities of practical activity in accordance with the achievements of medical theory and practice; efficiency and accuracy in performing work; activity, independence. It is such a nurse who can fully express herself in the professional field and actively contribute to the development of practical health care in accordance with modern challenges. In their totality, these qualities form the basis of the content of vocational training and, thus, act as an objective system-forming factor in the choice of the basic didactic laws.

Based on the analysis of textbooks and manuals on didactics, as well as professional pedagogy, two didactic laws were identified (unity and relationship between theory and practice; unity of teaching and development), which correspond to the conceptual foundations of the praxeological approach. Let us dwell on their characteristics in a methodological and practical plane.

The law of unity and relationship between theory and practice reveals "the relationship between the content and methods of teaching and future activities" (*Yahupov V. V. 2003, p. 283*). It proves the significant influence of practice on the professionalism of a future specialist and fully meets the basic requirements of praxeology. According to this law, it is advisable to make training sessions with future nurses-bachelors as professionally oriented as possible. The law of unity and interrelation of theory and practice is implemented with the help of practical methods and forms of organizing educational and cognitive activities of students.

Let us present the characteristics of another law - the law of the unity of learning and development. It is a well-known fact that learning activates thought processes and encourages a person to develop. Based on this, an essential feature of learning is that it creates a zone of "proximal development" and sets in motion a number of internal processes of the individual. In the context of this law, the educational process in higher medical educational institutions, where future nurses-bachelors are educated, should be

focused on the potential development of students based on filling with pedagogical innovations.

The essence of the law lies in the fact that the development of personality can only occur in activity - that is, in learning. Moreover, training that provides better development can be considered successful. Pedagogically balanced learning assumes that students who have acquired general medical knowledge can significantly deepen the spectrum of theoretical and practical knowledge based on in-depth study of professionally oriented disciplines. This approach will lead to the emergence of complex mental processes of thinking and will contribute to improving the personal and professional development of future mid-level medicine specialists.

In the process of studying the position of praxeology (Yu. Bogoyavlenskaya, V. Didenko L. Insekomoe, A. Lyubogor, N. Satsky, etc.) it was found that it is advisable to add the following three laws to the specified list of general didactic laws: the relationship of socialization and professionalization of the individual in the learning process; combination of integration and differentiation; close interaction of theoretical and practical training. Let's consider their essence and give a brief description of their implementation in the educational process.

The law of the relationship between socialization and professionalization of the individual in the learning process. Let us emphasize that the conceptual field of the relationship between socialization and professionalization is formed within the framework of research by scientists on the problems of personality socialization, a systematic approach to the study of the processes of development and education of a personality, professional formation of a personality, as well as professional self-determination of a personality. We support the position of E. Lapochkin (*Lapochkin E. V. 2005, p. 88-89*) that the integrative nature of the relationship between socialization and professionalization of future mid-level medical specialists with the leading role of pedagogical regulation of these processes is determined by the following requirements:

- the need to move from the normative external pedagogical regulation of the formation of the personality of medical students to its internal self-regulation based on the development of reflexive mechanisms of thinking and self-awareness in professional activity (self-esteem, self-control), as well as the formation of internal professional-value and normative orientations of the personality;

- development of the operational basis of professional activity (professional skills) based on the use of independence in the assimilation of knowledge, awareness of the values of the work of a nurse, the weight of practical experience and gaining public recognition as a way of becoming a nurse as a subject of labor;

- achievement of the social and professional maturity of the individual as the optimal personal and social result of professional socialization, an indicator of which is the coincidence of life ideals, values, aspirations of a specialist in his professional vocation and the status of the profession of a bachelor's nurse.

The law of combination of integration and differentiation. First of all, we note that the unity of integration and differentiation in the professional training of future medical workers has opportunities that are due to the socio-economic development of health care and the formation of future nursing specialists' readiness for professional activity. Integration is an important lever for optimizing the result of professional training of nurses and serves as a means of increasing the effectiveness of mastering the basics of professional skills.

For professional training in the educational environment of a medical educational institution, the basis is the integration of science, medicine and the practical sphere of healthcare. In our vision, the role of integration is that it turns out to be the subject of conscious management. The meaning and functions of integration and differentiation of professional training are revealed when analyzing the specialties of nurses, researching the problem of the unity of theory and practice.

The mechanisms of integration are mediated by its connection with differentiation, and their only existence is especially clearly manifested at such levels of organization of the educational process in medical institutions:

1) the consistency of the content of vocational training with the allocation of a universal (general) and differentiated (special) part, which is reflected in the education standard and the construction of educational and program documentation;

2) interaction of the content of academic subjects based on the unity and synthesis of sciences in the system "society - science - practical health care";

3) the integrity of the vocational training process, which is determined by the commonality of medicine and practical health care;

4) the invariance of structural components in the content of training, acts as a translator of all previous levels;

5) the connection between theory and practice, determines the main areas and problem reference points of the relationships in the process of professional training of future nurses-bachelors;

6) the unity of pedagogical concepts and theories based on the use of a praxeological approach (for example, the concept of the unity of the laws of pedagogy and the laws of practical health care, the theory of the relationship between general and vocational education, etc.).

In general, the combination of differentiation and integration is directly manifested in the implementation of the laws of pedagogy and the laws of practical training, the development of pedagogical theories in the context of the synthesis of ideas for the formation of the personality of a qualified specialist in nursing.

The law of close interaction of theoretical and practical training provides that the basis for the unity and interaction of two processes (theoretical training and practical training) are the goals of forming the personality of future nurses-bachelors based on the development of their professional skills. In the practical plane, the interconnection of goals occurs through the development of science, medicine, practical health care, that is, categories that ensure the interaction of theoretical and practical processes.

We focus on the fact that in a health care environment, practical training covers the passage of educational practice by students on the basis of medical institutions in the profile of their specialty, as well as pre-diploma practice (in the therapeutic, surgical and children's departments). Thus, in the methodological plane, common goals are realized through a combination of theoretical training (knowledge) with practical training (skills and abilities). In the conditions of professional training of future nurses-bachelors, these processes occur through interpenetration at all stages of education. To ensure the unity of the educational process with practical training and facts of the development of practical health care, medicine, science, vocational education, trends and forecasts are of decisive importance.

In the process of establishing the close interaction between theoretical and practical training, the following facts must be taken into account:

- practice should be supported by solid theoretical knowledge;
- when organizing practice for future nurses-bachelors, it is necessary to expand, deepen and consolidate the theoretical knowledge that is necessary for mastering the relevant medical specialty;
- the combination of theoretical and practical training will be successful only if the cognitive and practical tasks that meet the requirements of the curriculum are comprehensively solved, taking into account the characteristics of professional activity.

Conclusions. That is, in the most general sense, the educational process in higher medical institutions provides for interaction and is laid down in structuring the content of education. At the same time, a prerequisite is the introduction of the latest medical technologies, achievements in practical health care, along with general requirements for the training of nursing specialists.

In our understanding, the above didactic laws (unity and relationship between theory and practice; unity of learning and development; relationship between socialization and professionalization of a person in the learning process, a combination of integration and differentiation; close interaction of theoretical and practical training) convincingly confirm the proposed assumption that the goal and the content of professional training of future nurses-bachelors, depending on the needs of society, and also proves the need to create appropriate conditions to ensure the operation of these laws. From our point of view, the practical implementation of the highlighted didactic laws in the professional training of future nurses-bachelors will help teachers of higher medical education to reasonably organize the content of the educational process, will allow to outline the most promising ways and pedagogical means that will lead to the optimization of the process of forming students' readiness for professional activity.

Prospects for further searches will be aimed at studying practical approaches to the choice of organizational and pedagogical conditions, it is advisable to put the readiness for professional activity in future bachelors of nursing as a basis for forming.

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